

Workplace Well-being, Perceived Social Support, and Stress among Healthcare Professionals in High and Low-exposure Units: A Comparative Study

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Healthcare professionals across the globe often work in challenging environments, thus they are more susceptible to face high levels of stress and low levels of workplace well-being. This risk becomes even more adverse for those working in high-exposure units, like COVID-designated wards, as they have to encounter additional physical and mental difficulties on duty. The aim of this study is to examine workplace well-being, perceived social support and stress among healthcare workers posted in high and low exposure hospital units. The researcher assessed a total of 220 healthcare workers, out of which 110 participants were posted in high-exposure units and 110 participants were posted in low-exposure units. The participants completed standardized assessments that measured mental well-being, social support, and perceived stress. Results and conclusion: Healthcare workers posted in high-exposure units had significantly lower levels of workplace well-being and perceived social support, while also having high levels of stress as compared to workers posted in low-exposure units. Additionally, it was found that social support had a positive correlation with workplace well-being and a negative correlation with stress. Thus, there is a need for emphasis on providing supportive work environments to lower stress and improve workplace well-being.

Keywords: Well-being, perceived social support, stress, mental health, healthcare professionals, exposure units

Individuals working in the healthcare sector in India and across the globe have to encounter physically and emotionally demanding situations at workplace. They are often overworked, dealing with staff shortage, long shifts and managing heavy patient loads. During public health crisis situations like the COVID-19 pandemic, these factors become even greater source of distress as the healthcare systems are pushed to their limits. The mental and physical health of healthcare workers requires attention in these circumstances. This is important not only for the well-being of the workers themselves but also for the standard and security of patient care.

When we talk about workplace well-being in healthcare it is much more than just liking your job. It means feeling emotionally steady, having support from others, and being able to handle the demands of the work (Diener & Seligman, 2004). Studies have consistently shown that medical workers with lower well-being are more likely to feel less interested in their work, face burnout and as a result quit (Shanafelt et al., 2020; Prasad et al., 2021). Social support, as it is perceived, refers to the degree to which individuals believe they receive emotional, informational, or tangible assistance from others. Studies to date indicate that factors like good workplace relations, effective leadership, and good teamwork are linked to better mental health, less absenteeism, and better patient care (Anwar et al., 2022; Saragih et al., 2021).

Healthcare workers in high-risk areas like COVID wards,

emergency rooms, and intensive care units faced extra risks of both mental and physical stressors like fear of infection, worry about spreading illness to their families, seeing death and suffering, and being isolated because of quarantine. Several studies from India and other countries have found that healthcare professionals working on the frontline experienced more stress, anxiety, depression, and sleep problems during crisis periods (Kang et al., 2020; Rossi et al., 2020).

The JD-R model is useful in this context since it offers a simple way to organize the different stressors and supportive factors that the healthcare workers experience in their daily work-day. During patient care, emotional load (e.g., patient suffering), time urgency (e.g., emergency cases) and physical risks (e.g., infection exposure) function as job demands. If demands are greater than resources, employees may experience burnout, emotional exhaustion, and lower productivity (Demerouti et al., 2001; Bakker & Demerouti, 2007). But when resources are plentiful, motivation, resilience, and job satisfaction can improve. The JD-R model helps healthcare professionals in all types of units see how their work environment shapes well-being, stress, and social support (Bakker & Demerouti, 2017; Lesener et al., 2019). Let's look at an example, if a teacher's job demands (e.g., workload, classroom management) are on the higher side but they also have strong resources (e.g., support, materials), the teacher would be more likely to stay motivated and engaged. On the contrary, if demands are high and resources are low; the teacher may experience stress or burnout.

In recent times, mental health seems to be getting more attention among healthcare workers in India, especially since the pandemic. The author, through this research has tried to add to the current body of knowledge by empirically showing how different exposure levels might affect psychological health of healthcare professionals. This study may also help hospital administrators and policymakers find ways to build resilience, reduce stress, and improve workplace well-being for healthcare workers.

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Objectives of the Study

- To compare the workplace well-being of healthcare professionals while working in high- and low-exposure units.
- To examine differences in perceived social support between the two groups.
- To compare the levels of perceived stress across the groups.
- Exploring the associations between well-being, social support, and stress across the full sample.

Method

Participants

The sample had 220 healthcare professionals from government and private hospitals in North India. The sample was further split into two equal groups:

High-Exposure Unit Professionals (n = 110): This group included health professionals working in COVID-designated wards, emergency units, and ICUs, where the risk of direct exposure to infectious conditions was very high.

Low-Exposure Unit Professionals (n = 110): This group included healthcare workers who were assigned to outpatient departments, general wards, administrative roles, and non-infectious disease units.

Demographic Composition

The sample comprised nurses, physicians, technicians, and allied health staff. Data was collected on age, gender, years of experience, and professional role to describe the sample and ensure diversity. Participants were chosen through purposive sampling because the study specifically required individuals with certain occupational exposures.

Inclusion Criteria

- Healthcare professionals aged 18 years and older.
- At least six months of work experience in the current unit.
- Currently employed and actively working in a hospital setting.
- Willing to participate and able to provide informed consent.

Exclusion Criteria

- Interns and trainees.
- Professionals currently on long medical or personal leave.
- Anyone with a self-reported history of psychiatric illness that may affect stress or well-being assessments.

Research Design

This study used a cross-sectional comparative design in order to achieve the aim of comparing differences in workplace well-being, perceived social support, and perceived stress among healthcare professionals in high-exposure and low-exposure units. The study also explored how these three factors are related in the whole group. A quantitative approach was chosen to make structured comparisons and carry out statistical analysis.

Measures

The instruments were selected since they are brief, widely validated, and effective indicators of workplace well-being, support, and stress, which makes them suitable for use during active working hours without disrupting the clinical duties. All the instruments that were used in this study have high validity and have also demonstrated high reliability in various healthcare and organizational settings.

Warwick-Edinburgh Mental Well-Being Scale (WEMWBS): The WEMWBS is a tool used for measurement of overall mental well-being. Each item reflects at positive feelings, how people interact with others, and psychological engagement using 14 questions. Each question is rated from 1 (*None of the time*) to 5 (*All of the time*), so total scores range from 14 to 70. WEMWBS is often used in medical settings to assess well-being at work because mental well-being is closely linked to job performance. A higher score means better well-being. It takes about 10 minutes to administer. High internal consistency with Cronbach's alpha usually reported between 0.89 and 0.91, indicating strong reliability (Tennant et al., 2007)

Multidimensional Scale of Perceived Social Support (MSPSS): The MSPSS is a 12-item questionnaire that measures how much social support people feel they receive from family, friends, and significant others. Each item is rated on a 7-point scale, where higher scores mean more perceived support. In the workplace, the MSPSS is a reliable way to assess social support, especially since healthcare professionals often depend on both personal and social resources to manage stress at work. It takes about 10 minutes to administer. High internal consistency with Cronbach's alpha typically ranging from 0.88 to 0.92 across populations. (Zimet et al., 1988)

Perceived Stress Scale (PSS): The PSS-10 measures how people see their lives in terms of unpredictability, lack of control, and high stress. Each item is rated on a 5-point scale, with total scores ranging from 0 to 40. While the PSS is a general tool for measuring stress, it is often used with healthcare groups and reliably shows work-related stress when given during active job periods. It takes about 10 minutes to administer. Strong internal consistency with Cronbach's alpha commonly reported between 0.78 and 0.86 (Cohen et al., 1983).

Procedure

The participants were reached out to during their regular work hours, and they were personally approached and given a clear explanation of the study's purpose. Those who chose to participate did so voluntarily, providing written informed consent before proceeding. Each participant received a questionnaire covering demographic details and standardized scales (WEMWBS, MSPSS, & PSS), which was offered in paper form. Administration time is 10 minutes. Confidentiality and informed consent were maintained.

Results

Descriptive Statistics

Table 1

Descriptive Statistics for Study Variables across High- and Low-Exposure Groups (N = 220)

Variable	Group	Mean (M)	SD
Workplace Well-Being (WEMWBS)	High Exposure (n=110)	47.20	12.85
	Low Exposure (n=110)	53.45	9.10
Perceived Social Support (MSPSS)	High Exposure	4.89	1.20
	Low Exposure	5.46	1.02
Perceived Stress (PSS)	High Exposure	22.05	6.50
	Low Exposure	18.92	5.00

As shown in Table 1, participants working in high-exposure units reported lower levels of workplace well-being and perceived social

support and higher levels of perceived stress as compared to participants working in low-exposure units.

Group Comparisons

Table 2

Independent Samples t-Test Results for Workplace Well-Being, Perceived Social Support, and Perceived Stress

Variable	t(218)	p	Cohen's d
Workplace Well-Being	-3.48	.001	0.47
Perceived Social Support	-3.16	.002	0.43
Perceived Stress	3.29	.001	0.44

Workplace Well-Being: Participants in high-exposure units reported significantly lower workplace well-being than those in low-exposure units, $t(218) = -3.48, p = .001$, Cohen's $d = 0.47$ (medium effect).

Perceived Social Support: High-exposure professionals reported lower perceived social support, $t(218) = -3.16, p = .002$, Cohen's $d = 0.43$ (medium effect).

Perceived Stress: High-exposure professionals reported significantly higher perceived stress, $t(218) = 3.29, p = .001$, Cohen's $d = 0.44$ (medium effect).

Correlation Analysis

Spearman's rank correlation coefficients were computed to examine relationships among the three variables across the entire sample ($N = 220$).

Workplace Well-Being and Perceived Social Support: A strong positive correlation was observed, $\rho = .59, p < .001$.

Workplace Well-Being and Perceived Stress: A moderate negative correlation was observed, $\rho = -.48, p < .001$.

Perceived Social Support and Perceived Stress: A moderate negative correlation was found, $\rho = -.41, p < .001$.

Table 3

Spearman Correlations among Workplace Well-Being, Social Support, and Perceived Stress (N = 220)

Variable	1	2	3
1. Workplace Well-Being	-	.59**	-.48**
2. Perceived Social Support	.59**	-	-.41**
3. Perceived Stress	-.48**	-.41**	-

Note. $p < .001$ (two-tailed)

Discussion

This study looked at the workplace well-being, perceived social support and stress levels among healthcare workers in high-exposure units and low exposure-units. The results of the study indicated drastic differences between the two groups. Participants deployed in high-exposure units showed lower workplace well-being and perceived social support, as well as higher levels of stress, as compared to participants working in low-exposure units. Consistent with findings reported among frontline healthcare staff during infectious disease outbreaks (Lai et al., 2020; Vizheh et al., 2020).

This study holds significance as factors like social support from others helps protect workers' health. This aligns with the stress-buffering hypothesis of social support and empirical findings showing that perceived support reduces psychological distress

(Cohen & Wills, 1985; Grey et al., 2020). Healthcare workers in high-risk roles may have fewer chances to talk informally with others, may pull away from others because they are tired or burned out, or may even feel some stigma for working with infectious patients. Earlier research shows that frontline workers often feel alone both at work and at home (Rossi et al., 2020). The current findings support the idea that social support helps reduce stress and builds strength to cope. The link between support and well-being, and the opposite link between support and stress, fit well with this idea.

Stress levels were also clearly higher in high-exposure units. This is not surprising. Shift work, unpredictable patient needs, emotional labour, fear of infection, and the demands of critical care all contribute to sustained stress. Similar patterns have been documented in other healthcare systems, particularly in intensive care and COVID-designated units (Serrano-Ripoll et al., 2020). This study adds to that evidence by showing that elevated stress remains even when there is no immediate crisis. Longitudinal research suggests that psychological strain in healthcare settings often persists beyond peak crisis periods (Morgantini et al., 2020). Limitations of the study include; less sample size, personal resilience, team culture, and leadership style, as these factors may also influence the outcomes.

Conclusion

The study found that the high-exposure environments in medical settings are linked to low workplace well-being and perceived social support, as well as higher levels of stress among workers posted in these units. At the same time, social support stands out as a key protective factor. Preventive measures like regular psychological check-ins, group counselling sessions, and team building sessions, can help these workers take better care of their psychological health, leading to better patient care.

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